

SATELLITE MONITORING OF ANTHROPOGENIC PROCESSES AND FACTORS OF LAND DEGRADATION IN UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the research lies in the fact that the well-being of the Ukrainian nation, present and future generations, largely depends on the preservation of existing ecosystems, their support, and the enhancement of their quality and biodiversity. Particular attention should be paid to the problem of land cover degradation. Land cover currently holds a unique status regarding food security and is a dominant source for renewing crucial biospheric functions, ensuring the diversity of living organisms.

The anthropogenic and technological pressure on Ukraine's environment (land cover) exceeds several times the corresponding indicators in developed countries. A remote sensing data methodology was proposed to assess the impact of human, technical activities (anthropogenic predictor) on land cover degradation.

As a result of the research, the obtained data allowed for the assessment of Ukraine's land cover status and revealed the degree of its degradation caused by the influence of anthropogenic factors, namely, irrational agricultural practices, non-efficient long-term exploitation of mineral deposits, ineffective urban infrastructure design, irrational practices in forestry and park management, the influence of reservoirs, forest, and steppe fires, as well as military activities.

Keywords: land cover degradation, degradation factors, anthropogenic influence, site, remote sensing data.

INTRODUCTION

All human life ultimately depends on the earth. The earth provides people with the means to live, and from the very beginning, it became a source of important resources. But in the modern world, the earth is no longer able to cope with the pressure of human activity on its limited resources, and leads to land degradation. The geographic scale of degradation processes covers all terrestrial regions and biomes of the world, with the exception of only the continent of Antarctica. This covers the full range of human-modified systems, including, but not limited to, drylands, agricultural and agroforestry systems, forests, and associated water systems. This includes wetlands and aquifer systems, including saline systems as well as areas of swamps, peat bogs, natural or artificial reservoirs, permanent or temporary, with static or flowing and fresh water, etc [1-5].

An actual problem is land degradation in the territory of Ukraine, in particular, caused by human activity. Identification of areas subject to degradation and factors that have the greatest negative impact on the country's land cover is one of the important tasks.

The development of information technologies, the emergence of high- and ultra-high-resolution satellite images, the development of methods, and improvements in models

of geodetic equipment have led to qualitative changes in methods for assessing land cover degradation. In this regard, recently remote sensing methods and geographic information technologies have become the leading methods for assessing land cover degradation.

The purpose of this research is to identify, assess, and analyze the anthropogenic component (human technical activities) of the process of land cover degradation in Ukraine using remote sensing materials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed algorithm for estimating the anthropogenic load on the land cover of Ukraine using satellite information. The work algorithm consists of the following stages: 1) obtaining remote zoning data of the Earth for the study area; 2) initial processing of satellite survey data using the Erdas Imagine program; 3) selection of the territory of Ukraine by vector layer from the vector map "Ukraine 500" and selection of the studied area territory according to the set contour using the Subset function of the Erdas Imagine program; 4) calculation, if necessary, of spectral index values and their differences using the Model Marker function of the Erdas Imagine program; 5) creating a GIS project in the ArcGIS program and presenting all input and calculation data; 6) creation of the original image using the Layout function of the ArcGIS program with the addition of geographic coordinates, scale, and legend.

In the research process, remote sensing data from Landsat 5/9 and WorldView-2 satellites was used. To determine changes in the study area, data for a 30-year period were compared. The results of the research were displayed in the program for working with geospatial data, ArcGIS. Direct processing of remote sensing data was carried out using the program Erdas Imagine.

Quantitative and qualitative calculations were carried out on the example of the territory of the test site, which is characterized by constant industrial development (fig. 1).

Figure 1 – Space image of the test site and its location within Ukraine.

RESULTS

Since land degradation is a complex interconnected natural-anthropogenic phenomenon, an approach to identifying and understanding anthropogenic processes must take into account the driving forces and factors underlying the anthropogenic component of degradation. Based on information, bibliography, and analytical and detailed analysis,

Figure 2 shows the main existing factors of anthropogenic pressure on the natural environment of Ukraine.

Figure 2 – Main anthropogenic factors influencing the degradation of land cover in Ukraine

In Ukraine, the factors of land cover degradation based on anthropogenic load are provoked by the following conditions, which give rise to causes of degradation, and the very processes of land cover degradation in Ukraine are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Graphical model of the studying human technical activity (anthropogenic predictor) on land cover degradation in Ukraine

These are the following conditions: a way of life with an unbalanced level of consumption and production in a combined economy (in Ukraine, a mixed type of economy with income below the average, including the fact that full-scale military actions and her condition worsen), which also aggravates this condition [6-7]; unstable levels of expansion of agriculture, extraction of natural resources and minerals; urbanization; growing demand for food, feed, fuel, and raw materials, which increases the load on land resources; and competition for natural resources.

Based on the information provided (Fig. 2, 3), the impact of human technical activities on the land cover degradation processes of the Ukrainian was assessed using the following quantitative and qualitative examples (Fig. 4-5).

Figure 4 – Examples of land cover degradation processes in Ukraine: F1 – planar erosion caused by slope plowing; F2 – impact of long-term development of mineral deposits on land cover degradation. The red color shows the change in territory due to anthropogenic influence; F3 – impact of the liquidation of the Kakhov reservoir on the degradation of the land cover. The boundary of the test site is shown in red, and the boundary of the water table is shown in blue; F4 – expanding the agglomeration of the

city of Kryvyi Rih due to agricultural landscapes. The *red color* is the border of the fragment of territory where changes in the land cover took place; F6 – disturbance of the surface layer of the soil as a result of shelling and the creation of belioration structures (trenches and dugouts).

Figure 5 – Examples of land cover degradation processes in Ukraine: F5 – irrational forestry practice – deforestation within the forest strip on the territory. The *red color* is the boundaries of the territory change fragment; F7 – stubble burning in the territory according to data from the Sentinel-2 satellite for August 2022. The *blue line* is the contour of the burned area.

DISCUSSION

Human technical activity is now the most important force influencing the degradation of ecosystems in all major biomes in Ukraine. Long-term factors of land degradation continue to grow in most of Ukraine. Recent large-scale drivers of change, such as regional climate change and war, are further exacerbating their impact. Now the population of the country is in a qualitatively different and new world (compared to what it was only a few decades ago), and the totality of those factors shown in Fig. 2 creates significant problems for mitigating further land degradation in Ukraine. There are no regions in Ukraine that are currently free from any form of human influence.

In Ukraine, as a result of the long-term dominance of resource- and energy-intensive technologies, the unbalanced structure of the land fund, and the unsparing use of land, significant development has resulted in degradation processes (erosion), especially on agricultural lands.

Figure 4.F1 shows an example of the impact of irrational agricultural management on the degradation of the land cover, namely the development of erosion processes. Based

on the data [8], the consequences of erosion processes due to non-compliance with existing requirements are shown regarding the limits of establishing buffer protection zones. Figure 4.F2 shows the negative anthropogenic influence of the long-term development of mineral deposits, namely the change of agricultural land (1990, data from the Landsat 5 satellite) with anthropogenically modified landscapes, namely mud collectors and abandoned lands (2023, data from the Landsat 9 satellite). The total area of changes in the given fragment is 8.156 km². The paper [9] shows that the loss of agricultural land with an area of 13 ha is estimated at the monetary equivalent of 6.5 million dollars USA.

An example of a technogenic, ecological, and social disaster is the destruction of the Kakhovskaya HPP, which became a real disaster for a huge region in the lower reaches of the Dnieper up to its confluence with the Black Sea. This caused casualties among the local population in the flooded area, the death of domestic and wild animals, changes in natural and cultural landscapes, damage to buildings and infrastructure, and deterioration of water quality. The impact of the liquidation of reservoirs on the degradation of the land cover of the Ukrainian test site is shown in Fig. 4.F3. The water surface area of the Kakhov reservoir within the Ukrainian test site as of June 2, 2023, was 140 km², taking into account the average depth of the reservoir of 8.4 m [10], and the total volume was ~ 1.2 km³. As a result of the explosion of the Kakhovskaya HPP dam on June 6, 2023, there is no permanent water mirror in the study area.

The expansion of agglomeration of cities, and irrational construction within agglomerations also leads to degradation consequences of the land cover, namely, loss of primary habitat, loss of biodiversity, etc. Figure 4.F4 shows an example of the expansion of the agglomeration of the city of Kryvyi Rih over 30 years using data from Landsat 5/9 and WorldView – 2 satellites. The lost area of agricultural landscapes due to construction is 0.57 km².

The conduct of hostilities on the territory of Ukraine leads to catastrophic consequences for the natural environment. An example of the negative modification of the agricultural landscape from the conduct of active hostilities during the war in Ukraine is shown in Figure 4.F6. The eco-destructive nature of the war consists not only in the direct extremely negative environmental consequences of the war but also in the long-term consequences of a collateral nature.

Irrational forestry practices are the cause of land cover degradation. Figure 5.F5 shows an example of deforestation, the indicated deforestation occupies 2027 m². The territory of the test site is located in the Steppe zone of Ukraine and is forest-deficient.

The destruction of vegetation due to fires caused by the human factor is shown in Figure 5.F7. For reference: when burning straw and harvest residues in conditions of low soil moisture, not only plant organic matter is burned, but also humus - the most fertile surface layer of the soil, as a result of which its microbiological activity decreases. This is considered an extreme degree of degradation.

Therefore, the given quantitative and qualitative assessments of the specified degradation processes show that the territory of Ukraine falls under anthropogenic factors of the load on the natural environment.

CONCLUSION

The cause-and-effect relationships of the process of land cover degradation under the influence of anthropogenic load have been established. The driving force behind these changes is human technical activity. On the basis of the conducted research, seven main complexes of various conditions (factors) that affect the process of degradation of the land cover have been determined. From the identified factors, the causes that generate degradation processes were singled out.

The obtained quantitative and qualitative assessments confirm and emphasize the level of anthropogenic load from technical activities (anthropogenic factor) on the natural environment of Ukraine. The interrelationship of intensive development in agriculture, mining, construction, and other human activities caused a high level of degradation within the studied territory.

The proposed methodical approaches, with the use of remote methods, make it possible to obtain and understand the long-term processes of the degradation of the land cover of Ukraine with the isolation of the anthropogenic component of influence on this process. Also, this approach can be used in further research for a differentiated approach to achieve the balanced potential of the economic complex of Ukraine, especially during the period of the country's military reconstruction.

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